

COMBUSTION OF OLIVE TREE PRUNING PELLETS VERSUS EXHAUSTED OLIVE CAKE AT INDUSTRIAL BOILER. MONITORING OF EMISSIONS AND COMBUSTION EFFICIENCY

Michael-Alexandros Kougioumtzis^{1,2,*}, Ioanna-Panagiota Kanaveli¹,
Emmanouil Karampinis^{1,2}, Panagiotis Grammelis¹, Emmanuel Kakaras^{1,2}

¹ Chemical Process and Energy Resources Institute, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas,
Egialias 52, 15125 Athens, Greece

² National Technical University of Athens, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Laboratory of Steam Boilers and
Thermal Plants, Heron Polytechniou 9, 15780 Zografou Campus, Athens, Greece

ABSTRACT: The aim of the present paper is to compare the combustion behaviour of solid biofuels suitable for industrial applications: olive tree pruning (OTP) pellets and exhausted olive cake. The combustion is performed in operating conditions at one industrial fixed bed biomass boiler (0.5 MWth capacity) used to cover the heating demands of an olive mill. Combustion tests are performed at the industrial boiler for three consecutive days. During the first day the reference fuel (exhausted olive cake), that is normally used in the olive mill, is monitored whereas in the second and third day, the OTP pellets and a mixture of pellets and pulverized OTP respectively are combusted and monitored for emissions. Monitoring of emissions in terms of dust, CO, CO₂, NO_x, SO₂, HCl and OGC emissions was performed and compared for each different fuel used. Furthermore, the boiler efficiency for each biofuel was calculated for evaluating the combustion performance of them. The combustion of the OTP fuels led to lower HCl emissions but increased CO and OGC emissions, while the ash formation exhibited signs of reduced slagging. For all fuels the high dust emissions highlighted the need for particle emission abatement equipment installation, while the behaviour of the boiler efficiency was directly linked to the air excess ratio, indicating that improved automated boiler controls are needed.

Keywords: biomass, olive tree, agricultural residues, agropellet, emissions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Tree pruning is the established horticultural practice of cutting and removing selected parts of a tree in order to control growth, remove dead/ diseased wood and stimulate the formation of flowers and fruit buds. Currently, thick parts of pruning wood (over 5 cm diameter) may be used as firewood in some cases but mostly prunings are left on the field and are either burned in open fires or, less frequently, mulched in the soil. Olive tree groves are a typical crop of the Mediterranean landscape that generate substantial amounts of residual biomass. Prunings (branches and shoots of fruit trees) produced from the Southern European Countries amount to around 5.5 Million dry tons [1] from a total area of 5 Million ha of cultivated olive groves in EU-28 [2]. Until now, the management of pruning residue has generally represented a disposal problem, rather than an opportunity for additional revenue. Prunings are either mulched, chipped on site and left as soil amendment or, in the majority of cases, piled and burned in open-fires. However, olive tree prunings (OTP) represent an abundant source of energy, or raw materials for added value products, still largely unexploited. Prunings can be used as feedstock for direct combustion, gasification, combined heat and power (CHP), anaerobic and aerobic digestion [3-6]. In addition, they can be also used as feedstock for bio commodities (e.g. particle board by replacing wood, bioethanol, paper etc.) [7].

The utilization of agrosidues as a source of biomass is an opportunity for supporting the expansion of the bioeconomy in Europe. Among multiple agrosidues, those produced from olive groves represent a significant potential for many EU countries. Biomass from olive tree pruning could be used as fuel for heating systems in boiler, thus helping to mitigate CO₂ emissions and reducing the dependence on fossil fuels. It also helps with indirect benefits, such as the creation of employment in rural areas. Since these fuels usually have rather low heating values, low bulk densities and are disadvantageous concerning

their storage behaviour, pelletization of such materials represents an interesting procedure to improve their fuel properties.

Aim of the current paper is the combustion testing of OTP pellets and pulverized OTP at an industrial boiler of an olive mill and the investigation of their combustion and emission performance in comparison to other established solid biofuels, like exhausted olive cake. The goal is to evaluate whether OTP fuel can be a competitive solid biofuel that offers advantages to operators of industrial facilities in terms of increase in efficiency, ease of boiler cleaning or reduced emissions.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Boiler

The tests presented were performed using one industrial biomass boiler installed at an olive mill in Central Greece. The boiler has a capacity of 480 kWth. The boiler employs a relative simple fixed-bed underfed technology and is designed for combustion of exhausted olive cake.

2.2 Fuels Comparison

The OTP pellets (OTP_{pel}) were produced from thin olive tree prunings as harvested from the field along with the olive leaves. The olive prunings were harvested by mechanized means (integrated harvester/ mulcher) in Agios Konstantinos, Central Greece [8]. Subsequently, the harvested olive prunings were transported to an ENplus A1 certified pellet plant in Southern Greece where the OTP pellets were produced. For comparison reasons exhausted olive cake (EOC), the reference fuel, was also tested at the olive mill. Additionally, the company was interested to try to use OTP chips. However, the fuel feeding system of the boiler could not handle the particle size distribution of the hog fuel. For this reason, 2 t of OTP hog fuel, after being stored for almost a year, were transported to a facility that operated a hammer mill and

were pulverized. The pulverized fuel was also tested during the combustion tests (OTP_{pow}).

The first comparison is that between the fuel properties of the biofuels. Samples of each fuel were retrieved for fuel analyses prior to the combustion tests. Table I presents the main properties of both fuels whereas Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 compare the minor and major elements of the fuels. A fuel characterization of all three fuels was performed in CERTH/CPERI's laboratories in Ptolemaida by applying established standards (ISO 18134-1 for moisture, ISO 18134-3 for ash, ISO/DIS 18125 for heating value, ISO 16948 for ultimate analysis, ISO 16967 for major elements, ISO 16968 for minor elements and ISO 17831-1 for mechanical durability).

Table I: Main fuel properties

Property	EOC	OTP _{pel}	OTP _{pow}
Moisture (% a.r.)	17.0	6.9	22.7
Ash (% d.b.)	5.5	5.2	10.3
Volatiles (% d.b.)	75.3	79.0	76.9
Carbon,C (% d.b.)	52.37	52.00	50.87
Hydrogen,H (% d.b.)	6.30	6.08	5.80
Nitrogen,N (% d.b.)	1.56	0.59	0.97
Sulphur,S (% d.b.)	0.11	0.08	0.09
Chlorine, Cl (% d.b.)	0.24	0.23	0.28
GCV (MJ/kg d.b.)	20.58	19.67	18.93
NCV (MJ/kg a.r.)	15.52	16.92	13.10
Bulk density (kg/m ³ a.r.)	570	690	360
Mechanical Durability (%)	-	98.1	-

a.r.: as received, d.b.: dry base

Figure 1: Comparison of major elements (mg/kg, dry basis)

Figure 2: Comparison of minor elements (mg/kg, dry basis)

The ash content of the OTP pellets and the exhausted olive cake is comparable. However, the ash content of the OTP powder is much higher and this is possibly due to soil contamination during their storage for almost one year. Even though the exhausted olive cake has a higher heating value in dry base, due to the difference in moisture content, the as received heating value of the OTP pellets is the highest of the three fuels. During the pelletization of OTP pellets no additive was used (e.g. corn starch). Regarding the major elements, OTP powder has increased Ca and Si that supports the supposition of increased soil contamination. In overall, apart from Cu, the pellets are in line with the limits of ISO 17225-2 for wood pellets regarding minor elements.

2.3 Emissions measurements methods

The measurements took place over three consecutive days (12-14 February 2020). On the first day, the boiler was fed with exhausted olive cake, on the second day with OTP pellets and on the third day the plan was to feed the boilers with OTP powder. However, due to the very low bulk density of the OTP powder, the fuel feeding screw could not feed the fuel to the boiler. Thus, it was decided to use a mixture of 80 %w OTP pellets and 20 %w OTP powder instead (OTPMix). Prior to every combustion trial with different fuel, the fixed bed of the boiler was firstly cleaned from ashes, from which samples of ashes from each fuel were recovered for analysis. For all measurements, the procedures described in the corresponding EN or ISO standard methods (Table II) were followed.

Table II: Parameters measured

Parameter	Method	
TSP (dust)	ISO 9096	isokinetic sampling
O ₂	ISO 12039	electrochemical sensors
CO	ISO 12039	electrochemical sensors
CO ₂	ISO 12039	NDIR
NO, NO ₂	in-house	electrochemical sensors
SO ₂	EN 14791	H ₂ O ₂ absorber solutions
HCl	EN 1911	Cl-free water absorption
OGC	EN 12619	FID

Gaseous emissions of O₂, CO, CO₂ and NO_x were measured using a portable flue gas analyser equipped with all the appropriate electrochemical and nondispersive infrared sensors. Organic Gaseous Carbon (OGC), was calculated based from the measured TVOC (Total Volatile Organic Carbon) emissions, using a Flame Ionization Detector (FID). Finally, for the SO₂ and HCl emissions, a flue gas sample of known volume was split in half and each half passed through three scrubbers connected in series and containing appropriate absorber solutions (H₂O₂ for the measurement of SO₂ and Cl-free water for the measurement of HCl) placed in an ice bath.

The dust emissions measurements were performed based on the principles of isokinetic sampling. Flue gas was sampled using a suction nozzle and passed through a plane filter that retains particulate matter. Fig. 3 presents the flue gas sampling from the flue gas stack while Fig. 4 presents the filters after the dust sampling for all three fuels.

Figure 3: Emissions measurement ports and flue gas sampling

Figure 4: Dust emissions measurement filters after sampling for the three fuels

3 RESULTS

During three consecutive days, the combustion of exhausted olive cake, OTP pellets and OTP pellets/powder mixture was monitored. It should be noted that the operator changed the boiler settings each measurement day in order to accommodate the different energy demands and the peculiarities of each fuel. For example, the feeding rate was lower for the OTP pellets compared to the exhausted olive cake and when feeding the boiler with the OTP pellet/powder mixture the air supply was lower to avoid drifting the powder. Fig. 5 shows photographs from the inside of the combustion chamber during the combustion, the three fuels, while Fig. 6 shows the ash formation. As can be seen from the photographs, the flame produced during the combustion of OTP pellets and OTP pellets/powder mixture was brighter than the flame produced with the exhausted olive cake. The ash produced from the combustion of OTP pellets is more granular and non-melted than the ash produced from the exhausted olive cake. Thus, the ash from the combustion of OTP fuel is easier for removal/ cleaning whereas the ash from the exhausted olive cake can cause slagging.

Figure 5: Emissions measurement ports and flue gas sampling

Figure 6: Ash formation

3.1 Emissions

Main gaseous emissions and flue gas characteristics from exhausted olive cake, OTP pellets and OTP pellets/powder combustion at the industrial boiler are presented in Table III and Table IV. The results are presented for 10 % reference O₂ in order to be compared with the respective limits of Class 3 of EN 303-5:2012 for solid fuels heating boilers, with nominal heat output between 150 and 500 kW with automatic stoking operating with biogenic fuel. Additionally, the results are compared with the current Greek legislation for central heating. It should be noted therefore that these limits do not apply in the case of the olive mill, as the boiler is for process warm water. However, they are mentioned here for comparison reasons in the case of NO_x, as for all other pollutants the limits of EN 303-5 Class 3 are adopted. The limits are as follows: 150 mg/Nm³ dry dust emissions, 340 mg/Nm³ dry for NO_x, 80 mg/Nm³ dry for OGC and 1,200 mg/Nm³ dry for CO.

Table III: Flue gas emissions @10% O₂

Property	EOC	OTP _{pel}	OTP _{mix}
Dust (mg/Nm ³ dry)	585	858	915
SO ₂ (mg/Nm ³ dry)	<0.2	<0.3	<0.2
NO _x (mg/Nm ³ dry)	286	222	293
OGC (mg/Nm ³ dry)	1,102	4,366	3,560
HCl (mg/Nm ³ dry)	1.5	0.80	0.27
CO mg/Nm ³ dry)	11,478	18,163	22,273

Table IV: Flue gas characteristics

Property	EOC	OTP _{pel}	OTP _{mix}
Air excess ratio	5.83	8.75	4.88
CO ₂ (% dry, @10% O ₂)	10.4	10.4	9.9
Temperature (°C)	150	130	99.4
Flow rate (Nm ³ /h dry)	417.5	406.7	401.7

For all three fuels, all emissions, with the exception of NO_x, are higher than the respective limits for Class 3 EN 303-5/national legislation. With the exception of HCl emissions, the emissions for OTP in either form, seemed generally higher compared to exhausted olive cake. However, for all fuels the dust emissions are significantly higher than the 40 mg/Nm³ limit. In order to deal with the high dust emissions, a cyclone is necessary in order to restrain the dust emissions. Also, the high CO and OGC contents indicate that the conditions in the combustion chamber are not ideal. This conclusion is also evident by the very high air excess ratio.

3.2 Boiler efficiency

Based on the results of the measurements, the boiler efficiency (indirect method) for all cases was calculated with a simplified equation based on EN 12952-15:2003, considering flue gas losses, losses due to unburned CO and

losses due to radiation and convection. The following equations were used for the calculation of the boiler's efficiency (Table V).

$$\eta_{(N)B} = \frac{1 - l_{(N)GF} - l_{(N)COF}}{1 + \dot{Q}_{RC} / \dot{Q}_N} \quad (1)$$

$$l_{(N)GF} = \frac{\mu_G}{NCV} \cdot \bar{c}_{pG} \cdot (T_G - T_r) \quad (2)$$

$$l_{(N)COF} = \frac{V_{Gd}}{NCV} \cdot \gamma_{COd} \cdot NCV_{CO} \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{RC} = 0.0315 \cdot \dot{Q}_N^{0.7} \quad (4)$$

Where:

$\eta_{(N)B}$	boiler efficiency
$l_{(N)GF}$	flue gas losses
$l_{(N)COF}$	losses due to unburned CO
\dot{Q}_{RC}	losses due to radiation and convection [MW]
\dot{Q}_N	maximum useful heat output of the boiler [MW]; in this case it equals 1.16 MW
\bar{c}_{pG}	integral specific heat of flue gas [kcal/kg K]
CV_{CO}	calorific value of carbon monoxide [kcal/m ³]
μ_G	flue gas content [kg/kg fuel]
NCV	Net Calorific Value, as received [kcal/kg]
T_G	flue gas temperature [°C]
T_r	ambient temperature [°C]
V_{Gd}	dry flue gas volume [m ³]
γ_{COd}	CO content by volume of dry flue gas

Table V: Boiler efficiency calculation

Property	EOC	OTP _{pel}	OTP _{mix}
$l_{(N)GF}$	0.2826	0.3580	0.1554
$l_{(N)COF}$	0.0026	0.0041	0.0050
\dot{Q}_{RC} (MW)	0.019	0.019	0.019
\dot{Q}_N (MW)	0.48	0.48	0.48
$\eta_{(N)B}$	68.78%	61.38%	80.78%

The boiler efficiency when combusting exhausted olive cake was calculated at 68.78 %, whereas for the OTP pellet at 61.38 % and for the OTP pellets/powder mixture at 80.78 %. Boiler efficiency decreased by 7.4 percentage points from the fuel switch from exhausted olive cake to OTP pellets. However, a significant increase of the boiler efficiency occurred on the third day of measurements for the OTP pellets/powder mixture (12 percentage points compared to exhausted olive cake). The main reason for these efficiency fluctuations is that the boiler efficiency is directly linked to the air excess ratio. The very high levels of oxygen in the flue gas on the second day of measurements (OTP pellets) resulted ultimately in the lowest boiler efficiency. For all fuels the efficiency values calculated are considerably lower than the (not applicable in the case of the olive mill) limit of the above mentioned national legislation for an 480 kW boiler (83 %). The promising results on the third day however, indicated that with better control of the operating parameter of the boiler this limit could be surpassed. These results highlight the necessity of the installation of improved controls like lamda sensors and flue gas temperature monitoring systems, in order to increase the boiler efficiency and improve combustion performance.

3.3 Ash properties

Apart from the emission monitoring, at the end of each

testing day, ash samples were collected and analysed. Table VI presents the main properties of both ashes and Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 present the major and minor elements of the ashes.

Table VI: Main ash properties

Property	EOC	OTP _{pel}	OTP _{mix}
Organic carbon (% d.b.)	13.03	12.28	17.67
Inorganic Carbon (% d.b.)	9.57	8.75	7.06
Sulphur, S (% d.b.)	0.51	0.26	0.22
Chlorine, Cl (% d.b.)	0.03	0.03	0.01

Figure 7: Comparison of major elements (mg/kg, dry basis) in the ash

Figure 8: Comparison of minor elements (mg/kg, dry basis) in the ash

The very high carbon content of the ashes of all days also supports that there is incomplete combustion linked to the non-ideal conditions in the combustion chamber.

3.4 Fuel Indices

A further comparison of the fuels and the evaluation of potential combustion issues is based on the calculation of several "fuel indices" [9], which are presented in Table VII. The fuel index (K+Na+Zn+Pb) can be used as an indicator for the estimation of aerosol emissions. A portion of the partially volatile elements S, Cl, K, Na, Zn and Pb are released from the fuel into the gas phase during combustion. Fuels can be categorized in low (<1000 mg/kg db), medium (1000 – 10000 mg/kg db) and high PM1 emission range (>10,000 mg/kg db). Exhausted olive cake is categorized as high PM1 and OTP pellets and OTP powder as medium PM1 emission range fuels. The actual dust emissions observed were higher in the case of the OTP pellets, mainly due to the higher ash content of the fuel, especially in the case of the OTP powder. However, the increased index for exhausted olive cake indicated that although the total dust emissions are lower, the expected emissions of PM1 would be high and thus more difficult

to control using equipment for particle emissions reduction.

On the basis of the molar 2S/Cl ratio, the risk of high temperature corrosion can be assessed. 2S/Cl ratios <2 indicate that a severe corrosion risk has to be taken into account. All of the fuels studied do not exceed the limit of 2; hence, high temperature corrosion risk is expected. Finally, the index (Si)/(Ca+Mg) can be used to evaluate ash melting behaviour. It is known that Si in combination with K can lead to low-melting eutectic phases. Fuels with values above 1 are expected to have ash-sintering temperatures below 1100°C, so all fuels are expected to have ash-sintering temperatures above 1100°C.

Table VII: Fuel indices

Property	EOC	OTP _{pel}	OTP _{pow}
K+Na+Zn+Pb (mg/kg d.b.)	15,503.3	6,539.8	8,565.4
2S/Cl (mol/mol)	1.02	0.77	0.71
Si/(Ca+Mg) (mol/mol)	0.0501	0.1040	0.0639

4 CONCLUSIONS

In overall, the OTP fuel could be an alternative fuel for the facility. In general, the boilers that are installed in olive mills, such as the one where the emission measurements took place, are of a simple and robust technology, designed to operate with low cost fuels such as exhausted olive cake without serious emission abatement measures, either primary or secondary, since there are no emission limits applicable in this case.

In order to improve the boiler's performance upgrades are required. Installation of improved automated controls, e.g lambda sensors and flue gas temperature monitoring systems can improve boiler efficiency and combustion performance. Also, cyclones or other dust emission abatement equipment like ESP or fabric filters are needed.

Compared to exhausted olive cake OTP fuels showed lower HCl emissions and therefore the corrosion risk is lower. Also, the ash produced from OTP fuels was more granular and non-melting compared to exhausted olive cake, causing less slagging and making ash removal easier. Also, the PM1 fraction of the dust emissions for OTP fuels is expected to be lower compared to exhausted olive cake, making dust control easier.

5 REFERENCES

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6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research leading to this publication has received funding from the European Union Horizon Programme (H2020), under grant agreement no 727961, AGROinLOG (Integrated Biomass Logistics Centres for the Agroindustries). The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the authors. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

The authors would also like to thank the local Agriculture Cooperative of Agios Konstantinos- Lokridas, INASO- PASEGES and NUTRIA for contributing in the successful monitoring of the harvesting demonstration in Agios Konstantinos and the successful performance of combustion tests.

7 LOGO SPACE

